

Code of the Exam Scheduling System

```
from datetime import date
```

```
class Patient:
```

```
    def init(self, id:int, examRequest:ExamRequest, name:str, sex:str,  
    birth:date):
```

```
        self.id = id
```

```
        self.name = name
```

```
        self.sex = sex
```

```
        self.birth = birth
```

```
        self.exameRequest = examRequest
```

```
    def calculateAge(void):
```

```
        return void
```

```
    def keep(void):
```

```
        return void
```

```
    def select(void):
```

```
        return void
```

```
class Exam:
```

```
    def init(self, examName:str, examRequestList:ExamRequest,  
    recommendation:str):
```

```
        self.examName = examName
```

```
        self.recommendation = recommendation
```

```
        self.examRequestList = examRequestList
```

```
    def keep(void):
```

```
        return void
```

```
    def select(void):
```

```
        return void
```

```
class ExamRequest:
```

```
    def init(self, issueDateTime:date, dateRealization:date,  
    dateTimeCancellation:date, orderStatus:str, PDFFile:str):
```

```
self.issueDateTime = issueDateTime
self.dateRealization = dateRealization
self.dateTimeCancellation = dateTimeCancellation
self.orderStatus = orderStatus
self.PDFFile = PDFFile
```

```
def issue(void):
    return void
```

```
def select(void):
    return void
```

```
def registerExam(void):
    return void
```

```
def cancelOrder(void):
    return void
```

```
def viewPDF(void):
    return void
```

```
class ExamReport:
    def init(self, description:str, issueDate:str, examRequest:ExamRequest,
statusReport:str):
        self.description = description
        self.issueDate = issueDate
        self.statusReport = statusReport
        self.examRequest = examRequest
        self.doctor = Doctor(name = "Joao", numberCRM = "1234")
```

```
def issue(void):
    return void
```

```
def select(void):
    return void
```

```
def review(void):
    return void
```

```
class Doctor:
```

```
def init(self, name:str, numberCRM:str):  
    self.name = name  
    self.numberCRM = numberCRM
```

```
def issue(void):  
    return void
```

```
def select(void):  
    return void
```

```
class Resident(Doctor):  
    def init(self, yearResidence:str):  
        self.yearResidence = yearResidence
```

```
class Teacher(Doctor):  
    def init(self, academicTitle:str):  
        self.academicTitle = academicTitle
```